

Theory of Information Growth

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abstract: A gambler demon replacing Maxwell's demon at work in Maxwell's original thought experiment could, with the help of luck and at no cost of computation, violate the second law of thermodynamics, but even if that demon didn't need information in gambling, the demon would still, as with all other machines and technologies are eventually formed, regardless of all the physical parts that make them up from information and the efficiency of Demon's gambling is proportional to the level of structural information that makes him and which it turns out and through this paper that it is not possible to reach the optimal level of structural information required to meet the maximum working efficiency of the machine and thus the demon continues in work and overcome entropy as such

Keywords: thermodynamics; Maxwell's demon paradox; thermal entropy; economic growth; productivity paradox; semantic information; information series

I. Introduction

Productivity is the most important area of economics, yet is the least understood topic in economic sciences, the growth of labor productivity is the main long-run determinant of per capita output growth and improving living standards, it is the reason why today's worker makes much more than a century ago, because every working hour produces more output of goods and services, and since Adam Smith introduced the concept of division of labor in his book *The Wealth of Nations* in 1776, economic literature has not since made any similarly significant intellectual breakthroughs on productivity, with what followed this date from rapid and successive industrial and technological developments that have erupted since the start of the Industrial Revolution, have been ignored machines and technologies as, according to economic theory, external factors located outside a circle of the specialized competence of economists and it is more appropriately be handled by scientists and engineers, until the means of production, the main tool for increasing productivity became totally irrelevant to it in economic analysis, and as a result of following this line of thinking, economic thinkers of our time are confronting great difficulty in explaining the labor market and the noticeable decline in growth of productivity with the great development of technology witnessed by the industrialized

countries, led by United States of America since the beginning of this century until the present day, along with almost all OECD countries and many emerging economies that exhibited lower productivity growth over a similar period in a global phenomenon, it was found that the growth rate of IT capital per worker dwarfs the measured labor productivity growth rate, it's like the development of transportation results in a delays in the worker's arrival to work, this paradox is widely known in economic literature as the productivity paradox, thousands of economic papers have been written to explain this paradox, but none of these attempts have succeeded in providing a satisfactory explanation is agreed upon for this unjustified decline, the reason is that economists are trying to explain the phenomenon in isolation from its main subject. On the other hand, thermodynamics are the scientific field that accompanied the emergence of the Industrial Revolution and laid the physical foundations for the work of thermal machines, as well as providing a measure of their efficiency, and economists saw no importance in using it in economic analysis, which was invented to help engineers in the first place to make their machines more efficient and effective, but what thermodynamics may can achieve for economics is much more valuable than what it has achieved for engineering, as we will see in this paper, the work on it has resulted in a number of paradoxes, most notably Maxwell's demon paradox proposed by James Clerk Maxwell in his book Theory of Heat in 1871, which reveals in essence the close relationship between efficiency and information, which we will late see that it has deep connection with productivity paradox in economics – by revealing the nature of the relationship between entropy and information, and its effects of this relationship on the efficiency of working all kinds of machines and technologies, the second law of thermodynamics has interesting result about nature's attitude to information, extending to the roots of the conceptual structure of the information itself to go beyond the narrow perception of the statistical nature only of the second law –, and with the great developments of machines and the IT revolution the door opened for many ambitious experiments to build the Maxwell's Demon Machine, and besides the harsh criticism directed at the most famous proposed solutions to the paradox, the paradox has re-emerged on the scene again. However, the development of information technology that is highly reliable in designing Maxwell's demon machine to maximize efficiency of the thermal machines is the same that we see its failure to enhance efficiency in other designs according to the productivity paradox, we can may see that the productivity paradox is the key to the solution to the Maxwell's demon paradox, and the productivity paradox has a direct relationship to thermodynamics, as result to prevent the violation of the second law by the impossibility of any physical system achieving maximum efficiency in working with development at a certain level of development, including, of course, the supposed Maxwell's demon machine, which may necessarily solve the productivity paradox

II. Lazy Factory

Suppose we have an industrial facility in which a part of the workers work in operates the machinery, while the other part is working on its development, and if we consider that the increase in the production of machine operators is achieved by increasing working hours or by increasing the outputs of the machine used in the work by development¹. So

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{j+1} &= \left(1 + (1 + \epsilon_j)(1 + \alpha(\psi_j) - 1)\right)^{1+\beta} \sigma_{j-1} \\ &= \sigma_{j-1} \left(1 + \alpha(\psi_j) + \epsilon_j \alpha(\psi_j)\right)^{1+\beta}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Where σ is the level of production or the number of units produced and ϵ is the level of work according to the available technology conditions², measured by the number of working hours, for example, and α is the level of technological development, measured by increasing the amount of output at the same amount of input through the units of information, ψ amount of information and β growth parameter for both the level of work and technological development by same level together, for all $0 < \epsilon, \alpha < 1$, and

$$\alpha(\psi_j) = \alpha_j \quad \alpha(\psi_0) = 0\tag{2}$$

Therefore, at each development of machines, that engineers do in the machine development sector, it will be offset by a rise in the productivity level of the lazy worker in the machine operating sector for every production unit utilized by the machine even with the number of working hours remaining constant

And on the other side, with every development the machine goes through, it creates more complexity in front of the dull engineer that requires greater intelligence to carry out the next development, but in return it provides him with added information that was not available before to start every time the development at the same degree of complexity, but from a later point of knowledge, it raises the threshold of his technological production to a higher level than before³

¹ Technological development works in two directions, raising the level of work even while working hours remain constant and maximizing the exploitation of material production inputs

² The farmer in ancient Egypt, who use primitive tools in production, cannot increase his production, no matter how much he doubled his efforts at work, given his available means of production, compared to what the farmer can achieve now with the development he possesses in agricultural technology

³ In actual practice, all the giant tech companies, for example, have created obstacles for other new entrepreneurial companies that they did not encounter when they started their business, but on the other hand, the old companies when they started their business were not available to them the same amount of knowledge and technology currently available to the new entrepreneurial companies, which they themselves created for other new companies

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\alpha_{j,\chi}}{d\psi_{j,\chi}} &= \left(\frac{1}{1 + 2\Lambda\psi_{j,\chi}}\right)^{\frac{-1}{\psi_{j,\chi}}} \\ &= (1 + 2\Lambda\psi_{j,\chi})^{\frac{1}{\psi_{j,\chi}}}\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

By solving, simplify and from (2). gives

$$\alpha(\psi_{j+1,\chi}) = \frac{\alpha(\psi_{j,\chi}) \left(1 + 2\Lambda\alpha(\psi_{j,\chi})\right)^{\frac{\alpha(\psi_{j,\chi})+1}{\alpha(\psi_{j,\chi})}}}{2\Lambda(\alpha(\psi_{j,\chi}) + 1)}\tag{4}$$

Where $\alpha_{j,\chi}$ is the level of technological production at a fixed amount of inputs χ after the number of times development j and Λ a growth parameter. Therefore, the physical efforts or mental abilities of the workers do not contribute to increasing productivity to the decisive extent of the information in their possession, which is reflected on the development of their technologies and machines. and here the active role of information emerges, which is the frequent maximization of outputs while keeping the quantity of inputs constant, or maximizing efficiency, analyzing productivity in isolation from information, closely related to thermodynamics is what resulted in the productivity paradox, and we will see in the next section If it is possible to reach a maximum efficiency of machines – and maximum productivity of workers consequently – by the unrestricted growth of information based on Maxwell's demon work model

III. Productivity paradox the solution to Maxwell's demon paradox

According to the statistical conception of entropy, entropy is ultimately may be a matter of design and is therefore a subjective property that relates exclusively to the conditions of the observer. Suppose we replace Maxwell's demon in Maxwell's thought experiment with another lazy demon to do his work. But instead of doing his work with devotion, he will resort to luck where the devil opens the door over and over again to allow gas molecules to flow out arbitrarily each time without any real control over them. So that the equation of the lazy demon's work becomes this way

$$\sum_f p_f = \sum_{i,j=1}^{N+1} \vartheta^{\delta_j} (1 - \delta_j) p_i < N + 1 \quad (5)$$

Where p_f is the number of molecules that the demon will miss in passing correctly and δ The experiment parameter is zero if the experiment fails, or one if it succeeds. Thus, if the demon had luck or a sufficient period of time, the demon, and without any real control from him, could violate the second law of thermodynamics by reducing the entropy in an isolated system. Therefore, all the prevailing solutions previously proposed to refute Maxwell's thought experiment based on demon's work are meaningless now, and in the face of this conflict that may arise for the properties of entropy at two different levels, the need arises for a semantic information theory of thermal entropy or whatever the name is that unifies between information and the laws of physics to solve the paradox at its roots and there is another more pressing economic reason for its need is that all machines, technologies and beings are made up of three components, the material that makes up them, the energy that drives them, and the structural information on which they are formed. According to the first law of thermodynamics, it is not possible to obtain more work than the energy that was expended to perform it, and the second law places another restraint it is not possible to obtain perfect work equivalent to even all the energy that has been exploited and for considerations of scarcity in the economics, there is no possibility of endless continuity of work with unlimited open access of resources that can compensate for the shortcomings imposed by the laws of thermodynamics. Therefore, the only bet on increasing the production of the machine⁴ in any thermodynamic production process under the restraints of nature and the scarcity of resources is development by the unconditional growth of information to overcome it, after all, Information is information, not matter or energy

The feasibility of any thermodynamic system is related to what we know about it, we do not know of a way of how to extract energy, and then do mechanical work from tons of diffusion air molecules by an information engine, in contrast to a few liters of diesel fuel in an internal combustion cycle, and the entropy can be re-abstracted in the light of this perception as such. Let

$$\eta_{ith} = \frac{1}{Q} \left((1 + i\bar{\theta}) \sum_{i=0}^{j+1} (\alpha(\psi_{j-i}) - \alpha(\psi_{j-i-1})) Q \right), \quad \bar{\theta} = \frac{\alpha(\psi_j)}{j} \quad (6)$$

⁴ Maximizing its efficiency by improving its utilization of production inputs of material and energy

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ k=n-1}}^j (n-k)\bar{\theta} + \frac{i}{j} \left(\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ k=n-1}}^j (n-k)\bar{\theta} \right)^2 \\
&= \frac{\alpha(\psi_j)(j + i\alpha(\psi_j))}{j}
\end{aligned}$$

And

$$\tilde{\psi} = \left(Q \left(1 - \frac{W(\gamma_{t+j})}{W(\gamma_t^*)} \right) - \sum_{i=0}^j W(\gamma_{t+i}) \right) \frac{1}{Q}, \quad (7)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned}
W(\gamma) &\sim \gamma^3 \arcsin \left(\left(e^{-\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n \gamma^3} \right)^\xi \right) \\
&\sim \gamma^3 \arcsin \left(e^{-\frac{\xi \gamma^3}{2^n}} \right)
\end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

And from (7) to (6) conclude that

$$\tilde{\psi} = \frac{W(\gamma_t^*) - W(\gamma_{t+j})}{W(\gamma_t^*)} - \psi_j < 1 \quad (9)$$

Let $W(\gamma_{t+j}) = 0$ then (9) be

$$\tilde{\psi} = 1 - \psi_j < 1 \quad (10)$$

Where η the efficiency of the system or machine, and it is defined as the amount of exploitation of the work inputs due to technological development and Q it is the work input from energy and $\bar{\theta}$ is the arithmetic average of information growth and $\tilde{\psi}$ the information created by the system or the information lost by the observer and W the work done by the machine and γ Is the level of entropy and γ^* Is the critical or optimal

level of entropy at which it is possible to perform the best possible work and ξ a parameter. Therefore, the more the system moves from a state of order and less possible entropy towards a state of chaos and more entropy, the more system information increases, the less the observer's information have about it, and the lower the efficiency of the system consequently, and therefore the entropy stands in the area between what the system contains information and the observer's ignorance of it, It makes no sense to talk about an increase in entropy in worlds containing Maxwell and Laplace demons

And because our knowledge as observers of the physical system does not depend on our abstract senses to detect on molecules, but of course needs machines and these machines consist of engineering information, and at each increase in the structural information of the machine which is reflected in the form of technological development will be offset by an increase in the efficiency of the machine's exploitation of energy – This means that our increased understanding of the system is reflected in the image of our machine development and vice versa –. Thus it is possible, at least in theory, for the frequent growth of engineering information in the designer's mind to eventually overcome entropy in nature after an infinite number of development. Whether this can be achieved in practice depends on the logical nature of information growth. If structural information in the designer's mind increases increasingly, there will be an increasing efficiency growth, and if structural information increases decreasingly, there will be a weak efficiency growth, and before judging which of the two possibilities has been determined by the laws of nature, we need to refer to the objective characteristics of the semantic information of the observer first. It's

- Ascending: Information gain, as with increasing entropy, starts at a lower level and continues towards a higher level
- A continuum: Information is an increasing quantity exclusively, because a physical damage of the machine can occur, and in no way can be a similar damage occur to the engineering information on the basis of which the machine was made, once added information about the manufacture of the machine is reached, it can be kept and accumulated an infinite number of times
- Valuable: Information is indicative things it is superficial to accumulate it – every new information added – Quantitatively, but it is more appropriate to accumulate it according to its power or semantic content, if you hear the same information for the second time, you did not get any added information. Then

$$\psi_{jth} = \psi_1 + \frac{\psi_1(1 + \theta_1(\chi_i))}{2} + \frac{\psi_2(1 + \theta_2(\chi_{i+1}))}{3} + \dots + \frac{\psi_j(1 + \theta_j(\chi_{i+j-1}))}{j+1} \quad (11)$$

$$\cong \psi_1 + \frac{\psi_1 \left(\frac{1}{(1 + \theta_1(\chi_i))^{-1}} \right)}{(1 + 1!)e^{-\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{\psi_1}\right)^2}} + \frac{\psi_2 \left(\frac{1}{(1 + \theta_2(\chi_{i+1}))^{-1}} \right)}{(1 + 2!)e^{-2\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{\psi_2}\right)^3}} + \dots$$

$$+ \frac{\psi_j \left(\frac{1}{(1 + \theta_j(\chi_{i+j-1}))^{-1}} \right)}{(1 + \Gamma(j + 1))e^{-j\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{\psi_j}\right)^{j+1}}}$$

< 1

And what a truly amazing result...!! the more information we know about the physical system – or a particular thing – to maximize its efficiency by reducing its disorder by information, the less information we know about it to limit that, which is the same result that we got in the equation (10) that our information about the system as observers decreases with the growth of its information – that is, any growth in information is followed by a decrease in its understanding – and it is a restriction imposed by nature on the logical nature of information growth of the observer to prevent a violation of the second law of thermodynamics⁵, which explains the reason why for the poor growth of productivity despite the development of technology or the productivity paradox, where θ the parameter of increasing the information another unit, or the rate of addition to the previous information, which is a non-static parameter, the amount of which varies for each addition according to the amount of the input used in its synthesis, and χ_i are variable production inputs intended for the synthesis of added information, the great role played by steam trains in the industrial revolution in the past was much greater than the meager role played by the latest high-speed trains now despite the tremendous development that has occurred to them, and more clearly the first agricultural tractor to be invented will increase the productivity of the worker significantly in exchange for plowing the land with livestock, but the development of the second generation of tractor will not have the same impact on productivity compared to what the first generation has achieved, so the diminishing information about our knowledge of train systems by increasing them was the reason for this decline, regardless of the introduction of more and more physical additions on them, and accordingly (11) the amount of information becomes diminishing for each development generation

$$\psi_j = \frac{\psi(1 + \theta_1(\chi_i))(1 + \theta_2(\chi_{i+1})) \dots (1 + \theta_{j-1}(\chi_{i+j-2}))}{j!} \quad (12)$$

⁵ rely on Maxwell's demon working model through raising the efficiency of the system by reducing its disorder, arranging it by the frequent growth of information about the system in the demon's mind

The growth of information reduces the adequacy of its production inputs – that is, the amount of production inputs required for the next development process –, In order for information grows at an increasing pace will require doubling the production inputs for each new information added that is, the more the value of the information grows, the greater the amount of inputs required to raise the value of the information one more unit to increase the efficiency of the system or the machine, and this theoretical result is empirically proven accurately [1] And this is actually what appears to be a decline in productivity by constantly exploiting more resources to continue to obtain the same level of production as it is, all mechanical and technological systems⁶ face a decline in efficiency in the end with development, where the cost of obtaining or generating information added to develop the system to raise its efficiency becomes higher than the marginal benefit of the development, due to the decreasing value of each added information, which leads to a diminish in the marginal efficiency of each developed unit added or generation of the system, and thus the productivity paradox, the biggest intellectual dilemma in economic sciences which related to the decline in productivity growth with the development of technology, is a direct result of the logical nature of the growth of information that is decreasing with its increase

So what's wrong with Maxwell's thought experiment? It is that Maxwell erroneously assumed the existence of an ideal being or machine that could accomplish its work with maximum efficiency and overcome the second law, in a universe whose entropy is constantly increasing, there is no place for existence of omniscient beings capable of creating inimitable designs, If it is not possible to obtain complete knowledge about something, then it is unlikely to obtain any efficient design about it, we can't know more about the universe than entropy can allow us to know about it

IV. Conclusion

In this paper, I presented a more profound solution than the previous solutions to Maxwell's demon paradox – which are circular solutions that reconstruct the paradox with some restrictive assumptions to confiscate certain working conditions on demon in order to fit the already challenged answer: they did not seriously solve the paradox, but rather solved the re-proposed version of Demon's work in the original thought experiment –, in conceptually abstract and not technically limited, by proposing a new theory of information that unifies between information and the laws of physics, which I shown through that information is like the most other thing in the universe subject to

⁶ These systems can be a computer, a gun, a battery, a generator, a combustion engine, a lamp, an electronic chip, a semiconductor, an integrated circuit, a medical device, a drug, a vaccine mechanism, a manufacturing technology, a production line, an astronomical telescope, a space probe, a particle accelerator, a spectrometer, or even car tire

the laws of nature and thermodynamics as well, and that the amount of information that can be possessed is proportional to the level of organization only in the universe, and that it cannot exceed it to include disorder as well, which I found that this proposed theory has very important results in solving one of the biggest economic problems faced by contemporary human civilization, which is the productivity paradox in economic sciences

V. Remark

It is intellectually exciting that the biggest economic paradox is the answer to one of the biggest thermodynamics paradoxes and both necessarily explain each other, but to come to that conclusion is no more exciting than knowing the way it led to it. Economics concerns knowing the best means to optimally exploit our limited resources that makes us achieve the maximum possible benefit from them or efficiency in the first place, the same reason for which the field of thermodynamics arose, what puts us in a position in front of two scientific fields that share the same goal but from different sides and intersect in the same problem, which is computing, the development of computing threatens to violate the second law, according to the current vision of a Maxwell's demon paradox It is the same thing whose development does not give more, while in fact its outputs are less according to the productivity paradox in economics, so it is not difficult to see that the solutions of each of them are not far from the other.

References

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